

CHOICE OF METRICS IN ACHIEVING SOFTWARE QUALITY ASSURANCE

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ABSTRACT

The quality of software indicates how much the software performs its functions intended to bring maximum satisfaction to the user. The issue of software quality assurance remains a checkpoint for producing competent software products with fewer defects, capable of fulfilling the objective of satisfying the user. This study is geared towards this direction by analyzing the dependency of the software quality life cycle on software quality assurance. It also analyzed the basic concepts of software quality assurance, with which it deduced that software quality activities have to be a continuous process throughout software development in order to assure quality of software. This study further proposed a logic for choosing metrics during the evaluation stages. It concluded by positing that the choice of metrics should largely depend on the desired software properties and attributes, with the assurance that quality guidelines are not compromised.

Keywords: software quality; software development; software metrics; quality assurance; quality engineering;

1. INTRODUCTION

Software quality has become a pervasive phenomenon in contemporary digital society. Hence, ISO 8402 describes the term as a summative grasp of all the characteristics inherent in an entity on which the entity's ability to perform its intended functions satisfactorily depends [1]. Software quality reflects how much software conforms to requirements. In a broader sense, [2] defines software quality in a like manner as the ability of every software developed under professional supervision to conform to specified functional requirements to perform all expected functions that satisfy all documented standards. It therefore means that the quality of software gives an indication of how much the software performs its intended functions to fulfil users' satisfaction. The quality of a software product could be determined by a number of factors, including funding, product priority, motivation, and incentives [3]. However, users are expected to contribute some level of responsibility that would encourage the accuracy and completeness of all specified requirements of the software by expressing their real needs early enough during the development process. Such contributions will go a long way to assuring reliable software quality. A product of excellent quality is one that contains very few defects. This is because such a product is highly clinched to conform to the stated requirements to provide better user satisfaction.

Software quality assurance (SQA) is usually influenced by software complexity, software invisibility, and planning and development processes. These are captured in [4] as a software engineering process with its systematic approach towards executing all planned actions mapped out to ascertain that the process of developing the software or its maintenance follows an established functional technical procedure in line with the requirements of stakeholders within a defined budgetary confinement. Therefore, software quality assurance remains a dependable balance sheet for producing software products containing as few defects as possible. It remains a dependable strategy for monetizing software engineering processes [5]. This objective of software quality assurance is made achievable with the use of software metrics which are appropriate for unleashing the properties that give the idea of the quality of the software. Software quality assurance plays the role of providing an avenue for the evaluation and documentation of product quality as realized during each stage of software development [6].

Software metrics is a standardization function that ascertains how much software possesses a certain characteristic. Software metrics therefore serve as an assisting factor in the assessment and evaluation of software quality. This is because software metrics measure software properties with the aim of presenting them in terms

that would portray how reliable the software may be. In other words, software metrics help us discover the overall quality of software products. It further exposes validity, performance, analysis and fault avoidance within a software system [7]. We can therefore agree to define software metrics as a tool that represents the extent, capacity, dimension, amount or size of some attribute of a process or product in quantitative measure [8].

The quality of software, as mentioned above, is measured and calculated with the use of software metrics. Ref. [9] identified four steps considered to be essential in measuring the quality of software products: (a) define the quality to be considered; (b) define the fundamentals that qualify the quality metrics; (c) list information for the measurement; (d) measure and evaluate the quality metrics based on established fundamentals. These measuring steps, as identified by Nakai et al., acknowledged the fact that software quality is measured using software metrics. It is therefore important that the software metrics can unleash the desired attributes to be considered in software quality measurement. The objective of this study is centred on determining an ensured quality of software by choosing the right set of metrics that would show that the software possesses the revealing attributes. Effective applications of software quality metrics can help developers to detect errors. This is because metrics allow the developer to determine the customers' mindset by creating room for feedback and proper analysis of the feedback using metrics [10].

This work is divided into six sections. Section 1 gave an introductory note which presented a background to the study; Section 2 discussed software quality assurance vis-à-vis software quality life cycle; Section 3 outlined the basic concepts of the phenomenon of software quality assurance; Section 4 reviewed some literature on related studies; Section 5 presented a formulated logical procedure for choosing the right metrics, and finally, Section 6 presented the conclusions drawn from the study.

2. DEPENDENCY OF SOFTWARE QUALITY LIFE CYCLE ON SQA

Software products are expected to do the right things and also do things in a right way. In other words, software products have to do what they are supposed to do and must function correctly according to specifications in a satisfactory manner [11]. The meeting of these objectives qualifies a given software product to be termed "correct". The correctness of a software product essentially comes from the software's rigidity in adhering to the laid-down specifications of the users and developers without derailing from the originally intended functionality. This makes it essential that a software development process follows the standard software quality engineering process in order to ensure software quality.

Software quality engineering ensures that software quality assurance is maintained through the use of relevant validation and verification activities, including quality planning; execution of selected quality assurance or software validation and verification activities; as well as measurement and analysis to gather enough evidence necessary to prove the establishment of software quality to all involved stakeholders. This set of activities involved in software quality engineering provides user satisfaction, especially with the guarantee that quality expectations are met.

Software quality activities therefore have to be a continuous process throughout the development of the software product. This is important to ensure that every stage delivers the required outcome needed to achieve the overall system performing the right things in the right way. This is because the software quality largely depends on the quality of the process through which it was built [12]. This is also aimed at carrying out quantifiable quality improvement as soon as a derailment from the system requirements is observed. This makes it necessary that the software quality life cycle is effectively followed in such a way that every stage of development adheres to quality standards. The software quality life cycle therefore should be fashioned to produce software products that are of an acceptable level of quality.

Software quality assurance plays an elimination role in the software quality life cycle by preventing problems that could lead to negative impacts. For instance, during software testing, software quality assurance requires that testers must make adequate scrutiny to ensure that system performance conforms to its laid-down specifications. Once some form of derailment is observed, software quality assurance demands that corrective measures be taken immediately to remove the anomaly in the software code or even in the software design. This gives the confidence that software products contain fewer defects when released, achieved through early detection and modification.

Software quality life cycle therefore depends on software quality assurance activities with the aim of employing specific means to ensure software quality. These quality activities are summed up in a broader process that involves the engineering of software quality. This broader process requires that (i) all quality goals are mapped out quite early prior to development, (ii) all strategies that would give an assurance of quality should be adopted, (iii) all adopted strategies should be timely executed, and (iv) all executions should be monitored to ensure conformation to mapped-out goals [11]. This phenomenon shows that software testing is an essential action among

quality assurance activities, which in turn remains a crucial action among quality engineering activities, as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure. 1 Scope and content hierarchy [11]

3. BASIC CONCEPTS OF SOFTWARE QUALITY

Software quality assurance requires a couple of activities used in monitoring and controlling software projects to ensure the actualization of the confidence that the preset objectives are achieved. In other words, software quality assurance is realized via laid down guidelines or specifications aimed at ensuring the integrity and durability of the software product. By quality control, we mean comparing the quality of products built with the conformance of standards and the measures adopted when it is discovered that standards are not followed. Normally, quality assurance maintains a four-step approach in its course to accurately realize the specifications of a project. Fig. 2 lists the four steps as:

- a) Act
- b) Plan
- c) Do
- d) Check

“Act” requires the request for corrective actions on the differences that may exist between the expected outcome and the actual outcome of the process in review. “Act” gives room for the analysis of the differences, if any, with respect to their root causes.

“Plan” requires the establishment of the objectives, and the processes needed to be put in place to achieve the desired and expected outcome. In other words, “plan” ensures that the target goal of the process is met in record time.

“Do” involves implementing the laid-down plan while executing the process to achieve the target product. During this phase, we gather data for analysis and charting in the upcoming "Check" and "Act" steps.

“Check” involves studying the measured and collected results in the “Do” step and comparing them with the target goal as stated in the “Plan” to ascertain any form of differences between the two categories of results.

Figure. 2 Quality Assurance Activity Cycle

The four steps described above form a cycle that continues to run as the project remains in progress. These steps conform to the four basic concepts upon which software quality stands, upon which software quality is defined and assured:

- a) Customer intent and satisfaction
- b) Functional and performance requirements
- c) Understandability, user-friendliness and maintainability
- d) Non-deviation from specifications and standards

The concepts give the idea that customer satisfaction largely depends on meeting functional and performance requirements as well as ensuring user-friendliness. In addition, non-deviation from specifications and development standards creates a great room for achieving these goals. That is why software quality assurance is sometimes viewed as a deliberate strategy aimed at ensuring the fulfilment of laid-down criteria in developing a product, in addition to attributes applicable to the project such as portability, efficiency, reusability, and flexibility. In other words, software quality assurance continues to operate on the principle that it is meant to offer an enabling environment that provides the confidence that specifications are met during software process establishment and improvement in order that it yields products that are fit for use. The activities that promote software quality assurance are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Software Quality Assurance Activities and Benefits

S/N	SQA Step	Main Actions	Assured Benefit
1.	Act	Compare expected outcome and the actual outcome and correct detected errors.	Customer satisfaction
2.	Plan	Specify objectives that would achieve expected outcome.	Functional and performance requirements of product
3.	Do	Implement specified objectives using real data	Understandability, easy-to-use and maintainability of product
4.	Check	Study implementation result and determine whether it conforms with primary objective.	Non-deviance from specifications

4. LITERATURE REVIEW

Software quality assurance is an empirical outcome of software metrics. The actualization of this requires offering a measuring strategy through linking software metrics to quality factors [6]. Appropriate methods to apply software metrics in the quality life cycle, such as the work of [6], describe software quality assurance in each activity in the software life cycle. Lee’s study identified a research framework (as shown in Fig. 3) through which software quality metrics could be applied in the quality life cycle to achieve software quality assurance.

Figure. 3 Research framework for software quality assurance [6]

In research study [13], similarly identified software metrics are at the forefront in achieving software quality assurance. The study established the fact that software firms employ software metrics in improving the quality of software. This is a direct implication that the measurements achieved by software metrics identify software quality. The result is in line with the study carried out by [14]. The study asserted that how software is designed and the degree of its conformation to the design reflect software quality. The study further identified five variables that describe software quality assurance, including correctness, product quality, scalability, completeness and bug absence. That was why [15] described software quality as a combination of various factors. The study further investigated such factors and the metrics whose measures would determine the different quality factors. The study achieved this goal via two research questions. Firstly, the study investigated which quality factor could be easily approached to ensure proper measurement. Secondly, the study which resultant measure would be useful for determining appropriate quality factors. This finding also points to the central idea of the study done by [16]. The study used various literatures to analyze software metrics with a view to assessing their ability in measuring both the software product and the process that yielded it. The study was eager to discover how the software was designed and how well it conforms to the laid-down configuration. In research study [17], it presented software quality as the ultimate benefit of software quality assurance. However, the study presented software metrics as the determinant of software quality and further asserted that the software quality that is measured determines the metrics to be employed. The deployment of metrics insinuates providing empirical evidence to determine software quality. This agrees with [18] on the fact that software quality is best evaluated via test-driven development methodology.

As software metrics maintain their key role in the business of software quality assurance, their applicability in software development processes is highly perceived to be tantamount to improving software quality. This agrees with [19] study that attributes software metrics with the capability of increasing the knowledge that prompts the evaluation of software processes to achieve quality products. Software metrics therefore crave to reduce defects and errors to achieve their goal of software quality improvement. Hence, process metrics need to be captured during process auditing to identify errors and find a means of eliminating them [20]. Software quality is therefore of high importance in the contemporary software environment, owing to the increasing rate of software complexity and size. In other words, software developers are duty-bound to maintain test-driven software development to ensure proper measurement of the development process, the aftermath of which would be high-quality software products [21].

5. CHOICE OF METRICS TO ENALBE SQA

Software metrics are basically viewed as measuring tools for the evaluation of software quality. Software evaluation is geared towards unleashing the properties and/or characteristics of the evaluated software with respect to the attributes of interest. In other words, the attributes being measured largely depend on the functionality of the software as well as the parameters for measurement. However, the choice of metrics for software measurement must be made in line with the standard measures to conform to software quality assurance. (For instance, [22] considered six quality attributes, namely, reliability, usability, efficiency, functionality, maintainability and portability, to provide dependable quality measures in the course of delivering software quality assurance. Hence, their study was limited to the metrics related to the chosen attributes. This means that the metrics must be able to give reasonable information as regards software quality and simple use while ensuring that quality guidelines are not compromised. This is essential because software metrics ascertain how much a software system possesses some distinguishing properties. The so-called distinguishing properties form the basis for choosing the metrics to reveal the required properties. To maintain software quality assurance, the choice must align with quality measures. To assure quality, software metrics have to exhibit the following properties:

- a) The chosen metrics should be able to identify the characteristics which portray the primary objective of the software evaluation.
- b) The chosen metrics should be able to measure quality progress. This means that the metrics should create room for improvement both in the development process and the software product.
- c) The chosen metrics should be able to pose some challenges or questions that will lead to actions that have the ability of exposing resolving-based strategies that tend to solve the problems.

The choice of software metrics in software evaluation therefore has to be made to revolve around the four-step procedure of quality assurance to achieve the desired and expected outcome so that it will reflect the desired attributes that motivated the software evaluation. In light of this, a choosing logic is proposed as illustrated in Fig. 4.

Figure. 4 Logic for choosing a metric

Fig. 4 begins with the four-step approach to quality assurance to ensure that the metric to be chosen drives the objective of the software evaluation. A decision has to be taken after the analysis of the final outcome of the four-step approach. The degree to which the outcome conforms to the target outcome determines whether to choose or to drop the metric in discourse. If the metric is chosen, the logic cycle would be freed for testing another potential choice metric. Otherwise, the metric may be modified in line with the evaluation objective and would be retested.

6. CONCLUSION

The complexity, invisibility, planning and development processes of software products influence their quality assurance. This paper established the fact that software metrics can serve as an accomplishing tool for achieving software quality assurance. This is because it is proven that software metrics are appropriate for unleashing the properties that give the idea of the quality of the software. This paper further analyzed the basic concepts of quality assurance. On that basis, the paper deduced that software metrics have to be chosen to reflect the quality assurance principles for any software evaluation process while restricting the choice to conform to the desired software attributes in order to unleash the intended software characteristics. This was driven down with a proposed logic for choosing a metric. Further studies should reflect the streamlining of some chosen metrics and the establishment of numeric results as their proofs of competency in assuring software quality. It may also take the dimension of applying the enumerated metrics to identified software products to determine their quality values, thereby providing an idea on whether to recommend the software products or to improve on them.

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